

Primary Myxofibrosarcoma of the Left Breast in a Middle-Aged Woman: A Rare Mesenchymal Malignancy – A Case Report

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Abstract

Background Myxofibrosarcoma is a malignant fibroblastic soft tissue sarcoma that most commonly arises in the extremities of elderly patients. Primary involvement of the breast is extremely rare, often leading to diagnostic difficulty due to its nonspecific clinical and radiological features. **Case presentation** A 45-year-old Bangladeshi woman presented with a painless left breast lump of five months duration. Imaging suggested a benign lesion. She underwent modified radical mastectomy, and histopathological examination revealed a high-grade myxofibrosarcoma with tumor-free surgical margins and no axillary lymph node involvement. Immunohistochemistry supported the diagnosis, and metastatic evaluation was negative. The patient received adjuvant radiotherapy and remains clinically stable on follow-up. **Conclusion** Accurate diagnosis of the rare entity depends on thorough histopathological and immunohistochemical evaluation. Wide surgical excision with clear margins, supplemented by adjuvant radiotherapy in high-grade tumors, appears to offer favorable prognosis. Long-term surveillance is recommended due to the risk of local recurrence.

Keywords: Myxofibrosarcoma; Breast sarcoma; Soft tissue sarcoma; Breast cancer; Rare tumor.

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Introduction

Myxofibrosarcoma is a malignant soft tissue sarcoma of fibroblastic origin, classically described in elderly patients and most frequently involving the extremities. [1] Histologically, it is characterized by a myxoid extracellular matrix, pleomorphic spindle-shaped cells, and curvilinear vasculature, with a known propensity for local recurrence. [2] Primary occurrence in the breast is exceedingly rare, as breast malignancies are predominantly epithelial, while primary breast sarcomas constitute less than 1% of all breast tumors. [3]

The presentation of myxofibrosarcoma in a relatively younger patient further adds to its clinical rarity and diagnostic complexity. [3] Clinically and radiologically, these tumors often mimic more common benign or malignant breast lesions, leading to potential delays or misdiagnosis. [4]

Definitive diagnosis relies on histopathological evaluation supplemented by immunohistochemistry to exclude other spindle cell and myxoid neoplasms of the breast. [5]

We report a rare case of primary myxofibrosarcoma of the left breast, emphasizing the unusual age of presentation, diagnostic challenges and therapeutic considerations, along with a brief review of the existing literature.

Description of the Case

A 45-year-old Bangladeshi woman with a known history of hypertension presented to the outpatient department with a painless lump in her left breast, which she had noticed for the preceding five months. There was no history of trauma, nipple discharge, skin changes, or constitutional

symptoms. She had attained menopause two years earlier and had no family history of breast or soft tissue malignancy. Her medical history was significant only for hypertension, for which she had been taking amlodipine. She had never used oral contraceptive pills and had exclusively breastfed her children.

On clinical examination, a firm, non-tender mass was palpable in the outer quadrant of the left breast. The overlying skin and nipple–areolar complex were unremarkable, and no clinically palpable axillary lymph nodes were noted.

Image 1: Hematoxylin & Eosin [Immunohistochemistry]

Breast ultrasonography revealed a hypoechoic mass measuring approximately 2.7×1.9 cm located in the outer quadrant at the 3 o'clock position of the left breast, close to the lateral chest wall. The lesion was initially reported as suggestive of a fibroadenoma or an enlarged lymph node. Bilateral accessory axillary breast tissue was also noted.

Over the following months, due to persistence of the lesion and clinical concern, surgical intervention was planned. The patient underwent a modified radical mastectomy of the left breast. Preoperative evaluation was unremarkable, and the surgery was completed without intraoperative or immediate postoperative complications.

Image 2: Vimentin [Immunohistochemistry]

Gross examination of the mastectomy specimen revealed a solid, grayish-white tumor measuring 4.5 cm in maximum diameter. The lesion was located 1.5 cm from the deep resection margin and was in close proximity to the overlying skin (0.4 cm). The axillary tail measured $7 \times 5 \times 4$ cm, and serial sectioning identified 22 lymph nodes. Histopathological examination demonstrated a malignant soft tissue neoplasm composed of pleomorphic spindle cells within a myxoid

stroma, consistent with myxofibrosarcoma. The overlying skin, nipple–areolar complex, and all deep and peripheral surgical margins were free of tumor. All axillary lymph nodes displayed reactive hyperplasia.

Subsequently, the patient consulted another specialist because of restricted movement of the left upper limb accompanied by tingling, numbness and pruritus in the left axillary region. Further evaluation revealed a serum CA 15-3 level of 18.9 U/mL, which was within normal limits. Immunohistochemical analysis supported the diagnosis of high-grade myxofibrosarcoma, with a possible dedifferentiated liposarcoma component. A whole-body isotope bone scan revealed no evidence of distant metastatic disease.

The patient was referred for adjuvant radiotherapy and is currently receiving external beam radiotherapy at a total dose of 60 Gy in 30 fractions over six weeks. At the time of reporting, she remains clinically stable and is under regular follow-up.

Image 3: S100 [Immunohistochemistry]

The figures represent the immunohistochemistry prepared from the mastectomy specimen. These affirm the diagnosis of high-grade myxofibrosarcoma, with a possible dedifferentiated liposarcoma component.

Discussion

Primary myxofibrosarcoma of the breast is an exceedingly rare malignant mesenchymal tumor, and most of the knowledge about its behavior and outcomes comes from isolated case reports and small case series. Soft tissue sarcomas in the breast represent less than 1% of all primary breast malignancies, and among these, myxofibrosarcoma accounts for a very small fraction of reported cases. [3]

Several individual cases have been documented over the past two decades, emphasizing the heterogeneity in clinical presentation and management. For example, Ono et al. described a 50-year-old woman with a 3 cm myxofibrosarcoma that was initially misdiagnosed on core biopsy as a spindle cell tumor and subsequently resected with wide margins. [6] A case series by Chaturvedi et al. recently reported two additional cases in young females and reviewed the literature, emphasizing both the rarity and diagnostic challenges of this entity. [3] A historic case reported by Hocevar and colleagues involved a 58-year-old woman presenting with breast myxofibrosarcoma, further illustrating that this tumor can occur across middle age and older age groups. [7] Another report in the literature described myxofibrosarcoma initially mistaken for a phyllodes tumor, highlighting the difficulty in distinguishing these rare mesenchymal tumors from more common breast lesions based on imaging and limited biopsy samples. [8] In a rarer demonstration of male breast involvement, Amaya et al.

documented a case in a man in his late 50s with no recurrence at more than two years of follow-up after mastectomy and reconstruction. [9] While clinical and radiological findings are nonspecific, the majority of reported tumors share typical histopathological features: atypical spindle cells embedded in a myxoid matrix with elongated, curvilinear blood vessels, and high cellular pleomorphism. Immunohistochemistry is crucial to exclude other spindle cell malignancies, including malignant phyllodes tumor, leiomyosarcoma, and metaplastic carcinoma. [3, 8-9] The largest available clinicopathologic series by Hartel et al. evaluated 19 cases of primary malignant fibrous histiocytoma/myxofibrosarcoma of the breast and found that approximately one-third of patients with follow-up died of disease within months of diagnosis; larger tumor size and older age were associated with poorer survival. [10] Although the number of individual case reports remains small, these findings highlight the aggressive potential of high-grade tumors, particularly when diagnosed late or with inadequate margins. In terms of treatment, wide surgical excision remains the primary modality. Close or positive margins are a known risk factor for local recurrence in myxofibrosarcoma at other anatomic sites, and extended resection with clear margins has been repeatedly emphasized as critical for local control. Radiotherapy is commonly recommended in high-grade lesions or when margins are close, as was applied in the present case. Long-term monitoring is advocated because local recurrences may occur several years after initial therapy. [9] Overall, although individual reports vary, the current literature suggests that local control with surgery and adjuvant radiotherapy may achieve satisfactory outcomes in selected cases, while larger tumors and higher histologic grade predict a more aggressive course. Given the rarity of this diagnosis, each additional case contributes valuable insight into its clinical spectrum and management.

Conclusion

Primary myxofibrosarcoma of the breast represents a rare diagnostic and therapeutic challenge owing to its unusual location, variable clinical presentation, and histological overlap with other spindle cell tumors of the breast. This case is notable due to the relatively young age of the patient and the initial radiological impression of a benign lesion. A high index of suspicion, meticulous histopathological assessment, and appropriate use of immunohistochemistry are crucial for establishing the diagnosis. Complete surgical excision with negative margins remains the cornerstone of treatment, while adjuvant radiotherapy plays a vital

role in high-grade tumors to reduce local recurrence. Reporting such rare cases contributes to the limited existing literature and may help refine diagnostic and management strategies.

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